

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

A CROSSWISE RESEARCH TO EVALUATION THE CONNOTATION OF HYPERGLYCEMIA BETWEEN NON- DIABETIC VICTIMS

¹Dr Ammara Aslam Khan, ²Dr Rameesha Muzaffar, ³Dr Maemoona Abdul Jabbar¹Lahore General Hospital Lahore²Mayo Hospital Lahore³DHQ Teaching Hospital Sahiwal

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Objective: The objective of our study was to discover out the connotation of hyperglycemia between non-diabetic victims.

Materials & Methods: The project of our exploration was crosswise, accepted out at the Department of Medicine, Jinnah Hospital from October to December 2018. The quantity of victims selected by investigator with severe hit was one hundred and seventy one beside with an evaluation of hyperglycemia.

Results: The age of 171 victims were in among 43 to 64 years. The statistics of identified severe blow victims along with hyperglycemia were 44 (25.75%). Hyperglycemia victims, logged by the investigator was 4 (17.38%), 13 (29.56%), 15 (28.32%) as well as 12 (23.54%) victims separately having age group of 30-40 years, 41-50 years, 51-60 years and 61-70 years. Among 44 hyperglycemia victims, a number of men, as well as women victims, were 19 (21.35%) and 25 (30.49%) respectively. The investigator did not find any significant link of gender with hyperglycemia ($p = 0.173$).

Conclusion: The consequences of our investigation showed a massive percentage of hyperglycemia in non-diabetic severe stroke victims. The investigator did not find any significant link in hyperglycemia with age, the time period of disease along with hit form as well as gender.

Keywords: Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF), Hyperglycemia, Hit, Diabetes Mellitus (DM).

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ammara Aslam Khan,**

Lahore General Hospital Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ammara Aslam Khan et al A Crosswise Research To Evaluation The Connotation Of Hyperglycemia Between Non-Diabetic Victims., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Heart impediment and cancer are the overall greatest purpose of humanity laterally with hit as the third maximum normal purpose in the entire world [1, 2]. The supremacy of hit in the whole world in 2010 was 0.034 billion [3]. Alongside the decline in the incidence of disease in western public, the difficulty of hit in states of South Asia has persuaded as well as careful to growth [3]. Sedatives like, phenytoin thiazides, phenothiazine's, beta-agonists also consequences of pressure hyperglycemia are main reasons of Hyperglycemia while strong illness, while anti-regulatory hormone grows liver distressing gluconeogenesis. Investigator identifies the hyperglycemia though strong illness and could be the early scientific resistant of under stated invisible form two diabetes [4]. The vast capacity of victims may practice with hyperglycemia just after to strong compression like blow even in non-availability of earlier detection of diabetes mellitus [5]. Hyperglycemia while health insurance, in victims who are not familiar to have diabetes linked with opposing outcomes [5, 6]. The investigator originate growth in hyperglycemia later to blow though the early twelve hours, and again decreasing or established in among one to numerous weeks [6]. The conclusion of our study may sustenance surgeons in well in time handling of the hyperglycemia, with the primeval handling of hyperglycemia in hit victims, the clinician may be capable to decrease interconnections along with other difficulties of such victims.

Non-diabetics: Investigators professed all those victims who haven't any previous record of diabetes, as well as the overall HbA1c level, is less than or equal to (5.60%) on inspection as non-diabetic.

Acute stroke: World Health Organization describe severe stroke as "progressively rising suggestions (less than twenty-four hours of time period) of body single side frailness, announcement complaint, cranial bravery symptom and temporarily vague trait i.e. (GCS is less than 8/15) of brain in nonappearance of leading cause additionally to any other than that of vascular source also non-divergence CT brain showed injury of gray-white line, vast dipping clots and low lessening CSF, hypo crowding of blinkered cortex as well as basal ganglia and consistent brain materials.

MATERIAL METHODS:

The project of our exploration was crosswise, accepted out at the Department of Medicine, Jinnah Hospital from October to December 2018. Investigators disqualified all documented victims of diabetes mellitus, head shock victims, recurrent

occurrence along with hypertrophy victims from study. The investigator takes the suitable earlier record of whole victims along with dimension of body form index and BP (blood pressure) and also watched for hypertension with the choice of yes or no and fat and non-obese victims. The investigator also led blood specimen of every victim's glucose level was professed as well as logged as current or non-existing if the level of blood sugar is greater than 11.1mmol/l (200mg/dl). Researcher records all the evidence and data regarding to patient on already designed Performa made for the said purpose. Researcher feeds all necessary composed information/data in SPSS software and also measured SD and average for numerical variables. The investigator also measured frequency for absolute variables and utilized Chi-Square test for examination of relation. P value is less than or equal to 0.05, declared as cogent.

RESULTS:

Researcher performed classification of hyperglycemia for age categorization as well as constitute (4) age classes. Hyperglycemia victims, recorded by the researcher was four (17.39%), thirteen (29.55%), fifteen (28.30%) as well as twelve (23.53%) victims respectively having previously mentioned age category of thirty to forty years, forty-one to fifty years, fifty-one to sixty years and sixty-one to seventy years. The number of victims chosen by a researcher with acute stroke was one hundred and seventy-one in this research. The age of one hundred and seventy-one victims was in between thirty to seventy years. The number of diagnosed acute stroke victims along with hyperglycemia were forty-four (25.73%). Among 44 hyperglycemia victims, a number of men, as well as women victims, were nineteen (21.35%) and twenty-five (30.49%) respectively. The researcher did not find any important connection in hyperglycemia with age classes ($P= 0.686$). The number of men and women in our research was eighty-nine (52.05%) and 82(47.95%) victims respectively. The researcher conducted categorization of hyperglycemia to find out the time period of disease and made two categories. The first category time duration was less than or equal to twelve hours and 2nd category time duration was greater than twelve hours of disease. The researcher did not find any important connection of gender with hyperglycemia ($p= 0.172$). The average duration of disease was four to sixteen hours.

The number of victims having a disease time period of greater than twelve hours was sixty-one (35.67%) only and researcher declared hyperglycemia in nineteen victims (31.15%). The researcher also

identified hyperglycemia in twenty-four (25.81%) and twenty (25.64%) victims with hemorrhagic and ischemic strokes respectively. The number of victims having a disease time period of less than or equal to twelve hours was one hundred and ten (64.33%) as well as researcher declared hyperglycemia in twenty-

five victims (22.73%). In a total of one hundred seventy-one victims, the researcher identified Hemorrhagic stroke in ninety-three (54.39%) victims and Ischemic stroke in 78 (45.61% victims). The researcher did not find any important link in between time period of disease with hyperglycemia ($p= 0.228$).

Table – I: Hyperglycemia Prevalence

Hyperglycemia Prevalence	Number	Percentage
No	127	74.27
Yes	44	25.73

Table :02

Variables		Yes		No		Total		P-Value
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
Age (Years)	61 – 70	12	23.5	39	76.5	51	29.8	0.686
	51 – 60	15	28.3	38	71.7	53	31	
	41 – 50	13	29.6	31	70.5	44	25.7	
	30 – 40	4	17.4	19	82.6	23	13.5	
Gender	Female	25	30.5	57	69.5	82	48	0.172
	Male	19	21.4	70	78.7	89	52.1	
Disease Duration (Hours)	> 12	19	31.2	42	68.9	61	35.7	0.228
	≤ 12	25	22.7	85	77.3	110	64.3	
Stroke Types	Ischemic	20	25.6	58	74.4	78	45.6	0.980
	Hemorrhagic	24	25.8	69	74.2	93	54.4	

DISCUSSION:

In a research that measured the influence of hyperglycemia in acute ictus, gaining stronghold and other later to twenty four hours, researcher experienced that those victims who are non-diabetic along with hyperglycemia kept both at hospitalization and later to twenty-four hours presented huge rates of reliance, causality as well as brain hemorrhages. The number of diagnosed hyperglycemia victims in our research was forty-four (25.73%) and leftover one hundred and twenty-seven (73.27%) victims were free from hyperglycemia. The expansion of already diagnosed DM in intense stroke victims is approximately between eight to twenty percent. Almost 6% to 40% of intense stroke victims have earlier unrecognized diabetes mellitus [7]. The alter adjustment of the organism to hyperglycemia in twice categories of victims, with the beginning of variant phenomenon to overcome the hyperglycemia, with a previously managed adaption in a patient of diabetes, may analyze these variations [8]. Zahra F et al in his

research has diagnosed twenty percent stroke victims of hyperglycemia who were earlier nondiabetics [9]. In research of supra-tentorial injuries, diabetes mellitus was identified 24.8% victims, as well as a researcher, declared transient hyperglycemia in 36.3% victims [10]. Zahra F et al in his research has diagnosed that in non-diabetic, 58% had ischemic injuries, as well as 42% had intracerebral hemorrhage [11]. It is noticed that between twenty to forty percent of victims hospitalized along with ischemic stroke are hyperglycemic, frequently in absence of already identified diabetes [12]. Hyperglycemia is most usual in victims of intense stroke, present in almost sixty percent of the victims and is considered exasperate cerebral ischemia [13]. That is because of stress hyperglycemia or unidentified diabetes disclosed while an intense incident. It advances to the accession of additional cellular Glutamate, acidosis between cells, cerebral edema, derangement of blood-brain obstacles and addiction of hemorrhagic conversion [14].

CONCLUSION:

The investigator did not find any important connection in hyperglycemia with age, the time period of disease along with stroke form as well as sex. The consequences of our research displayed a huge percentage of hyperglycemia in non-diabetic acute stroke victims.

REFERENCES:

1. Dungan KM, BRAITHWAITE SS, PREISER J-c stress hyperglycemia. *Lancet* .2009;373: 1798–1807
2. Christopher SG, Janice EOC and Hilary L. Diabetes hyperglycemia and recovery from stroke. *Geriatrics and Gerontology International*. 2001; 1:2-7.
3. Woodward M, Huxley R, Ueshima H, Fang X, Kim HC, Lam TH. The Asia Pacific cohort studies collaboration: a decade of achievements. *Glob heart*. 2012 Dec; 7(4):343-51. Doi: 10.1016/j.heart.2012.10.001. E pub 2012 Dec.
4. Zahra F, Kidwai SS, Siddiqi SA, Khan RM. The frequency of newly diagnosed diabetes mellitus in acute ischemic stroke victims. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak*. 2012; 22(4):226-9.
5. Zafar A, Shahid SK, Siddiqui M, Khan FS. The pattern of stroke in type 2 diabetic subjects versus nondiabetic subjects. *J Ayyub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2007; 19(4):64-7.
6. Nadya K, Shmuel L, Hilla K. The Role of Hyperglycemia in Acute Stroke. *Arch Neurol*. 2001; 58:1209-12.
7. Ogbera AO, OSHINAIKE OO, DADA O, BRODIE-mends a, EKPEBEGH C, glucose and lipid assessment in victims with acute stroke. *Int arch med*. 2014 OCT 23; 7(1):45. Doi: 10.1186/1755-7682-7-45.
8. Yong M, Kaste M. Dynamic of hyperglycemia as a predictor of stroke outcome in the ECASSII. *Stroke*. 2008; 39:2749-55.
9. Aranda R, Seshadri S, Beiser A, Kelly Hayes A, Kase CS, KANNEL WB, et al. Trends in incidence, lifetime risk, severity, and 30day mortality of stroke over the past 50 years. *Jama*. 2006; 296:2939. Paid:17190894 [pub med - indexed for Medline].
10. Llibre J, VALHUERDI A, FERNANDEZ O. Prevalence of stroke and associated risk factors in older adults in Havana city and Matanzas provinces, Cuba (10/66 populationbased study) *medic rev*. 2010;1 2:20–24 https://www.heart.org/idc/groups/aha_mah.
11. Sleimani, Morandi a, Sabatini T, Ranch Off A, Ricci A, et al. Hyperglycemia as a predictor of in-hospital mortality in elderly victims without diabetes mellitus admitted to a sub-intensive care unit. *J am geriatr soc*.2008; 56: 1106–1110.
12. Szczudlik A, Slowik A, Turaj W, Wyrwicz-Petkow U, Pera J, Dziedzic T, et al. Transient hyperglycemia in ischemic stroke victims. *J Neurol Sci*. 2001; 189:105-11.